

SAINT JÉRÔME, TRADUCTOLOGUE AVANT LA LETTRE /

SAINT JEROME, A TRANSLATION THEORIST BEFORE THE TERM EXISTED

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Saint Jerome, considered the patron saint of translators, was a prominent scholar who lived at the end of IVth - beginning of the Vth centuries. He is the author of a monumental work composed of theological writings, translations, reflections upon translation, as well as letters. He is mainly known for his Latin translation of the Bible, a version which remains in use in the Western Christianity. Recognizing such a prolific activity may be important for translators and translation studies specialists. In this presentation we will also be giving a few precious examples of Jerome’s reflections upon translation extracted from his letters, as well as from the prefaces of his works.